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Industrial Oxy-Combustion Performance in Cement Kilns

Noureddine Mechaal
Process & Innovation Engineer
Technical Innovation Department
Fives Pillard - Marseille, France
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FIVES GROUP KEY FIGURES

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Industry can do it

MORE THAN
200
YEARS OF HISTORY

MORE THAN
9,200
EMPLOYEES

EMPLOYEES FROM
87
DIFFERENT NATIONALITIES

€2,101M
ORDER INTAKE

€2,281M
SALES

2,869
PATENTS IN 838 FAMILIES

MARKETS WE SERVE

ROTARY KILNS & CALCINERS

- Cement,
- Pebble Lime, Lime recovery,
- FeNi, Iron Ore pelletization, Zinc, MgO, Ceramics, Calcined Clay,
- LWA,
- Lithium, ...

BOILER PLANTS & HRSG

- Water tubes boilers
- Fire-tubes boilers
- Power Generation
- Oil & Gas / Petrochemicals
- Food industry
- Chemical industry
- HVAC,...

MINERALS DRYING & HOT GAS GENERATION

- Minerals drying & calcining
- Fertilizers
- Food & agriculture
- Chemical industry
- Gypsum
- Grinding mills circuits, ...

OIL & GAS

- Claus furnace (SRU)
- Tail Gas Incinerators
- RGG (SRU)
- Sulfur guns, ...

SUMMARY

1. Decarbonation strategic priorities
2. Oxycombustion in cement rotary kiln
3. CFD Studies: strategy & results

01 Decarbonation strategic priorities

FIVES PILLAR DECARBONATION STRATEGY

Hydrogen

ENERGY SAVINGS

and processes emitting less CO2

Biomass

Electricity

CCS
Oxycombustion

EXAMPLES OF DECARBONATION FOCUSED ON OXYCOMBUSTION

Oxyfuel combustion with ASF (CCS)

Air Liquide and EQIOM project in Northern France selected by the European Innovation Fund

Paris, France, April 01, 2022

Oxycombustion in Boiler (CCU)

90% of CO2 emissions avoided: launch of the ChOC demonstrator, a low-carbon industrial gas boiler

- 16 partners launch the production of the ChOC industrial demonstrator;
- Winner of the France 2030 DEMIBaC call for projects - development of technological building blocks and demonstrators -...

[Read the article](#)

02

Oxycombustion in cement rotary kiln

WHY OXY-COMBUSTION IN CEMENT, THE CO₂ CHALLENGE

Clinker Production Process

Pre-calcination (~900°C)

→ ~60–65% of total CO₂ from this step alone

Oxy-combustion + CCS process flow : cement process

CO₂ per tonne of clinker

~540 kg CO₂

Decarbonation (process) ~ 62%

~330 kg CO₂

Fuel combustion ~ 38%

Total ~870 kg CO₂ / t clinker

Cement plants produce around 15% of total CO₂ in France

(<https://cap-decarbonation.fr/fr/la-demarche-cap-decarbonation>)

The unavoidable CO₂

Even with 100% renewable fuel, ~540 kg CO₂/t clinker remain result of the chemistry of clinker production.

→ Oxy-combustion produces a highly concentrated CO₂ flue gas : ready for direct CCS without complex separation. A good way to capture the unavoidable process CO₂ and achieve deep decarbonation in cement.

INTRODUCTION

Context & Objective

Fives Pillard has supplied a complete oxy-combustion solution for oxygen-based rotary kiln operation in the cement industry.

Five Pillard supplied:

- **Burners**
- **CFD study**
- **Oxygen valve trains**
- **O₂ injection system**

CFD Modelling Approach

Extensive 3D CFD study of the full kiln system: Simulations compare each injection option and analyse:

- **Flame formation**
- **Gas-flow behaviour**
- **Heat transfer between gas flow and clinker bed**

Expected Outcomes

Clear comparison of O₂ injection strategies to identify configurations that:

- **Support decarbonization objectives**
- **Ensure stable kiln operation**
- **Maintain clinker quality and quantity**

PROJECT OVERVIEW - OXYCOMBUSTION DEPLOYMENT

Industrial Line

3 500 TPD clinker production line with ILC calciner

Novafiam Evolution — oxy kiln burner, 71 MW

Satellite injector for ASF (Alternative Solid Fuel) injection

Phase Deployment

Phase 1 - Dry line aero-combustion (base case)

Phase 2 - Switching to oxy-combustion with Flue Gas Recirculation (FGR)

CFD Scope

Multiple Oxycombustion configurations simulated to compare flame structure, heat transfer between gas flow and clinker bed with variation of the O₂ % at the several injection points

03

CFD Studies: strategy & results

O₂ INJECTION STRATEGY- POINT SELECTION

O₂ INJECTION POINTS

- **1 Primary Air**
Enrichment upstream of PA fan
- **2 Secondary Air**
Enrichment in SA duct, upstream of SA fan
- **3 Tertiary Air**
Single injector facing TA duct inlet
- **4 Burner Centre**
Pure O₂ injection at burner centreline

O₂ INJECTOR PATENTED DESIGN - CONFIGURATION SELECTION

Key requirement: stable O₂ concentration in each enriched stream, configuration driven by duct geometry and flow rate

O₂ Stability

Each enriched stream must maintain a stable, uniform O₂ concentration - no stratification, no pulsation

OxyCheck Regulation

Closed-loop O₂ flow control : real-time % O₂ monitoring at each injection point ensures set-point tracking

Single vs. Multi-Injector

- Small duct → single injector
- Large duct → multi-injector ring for uniform mixing

INLET DATA: KILN OPERATING CONDITIONS

CFD MODEL VALIDATION - BASE CASE

Validation performed by comparing CFD-averaged values at kiln back end against plant measurements, 7 independent physical quantities

Validation Variable	Nature	Gap (CFD – Measurement)
Flue gas temperature (°C)	Thermal: global energy balance indicator	-2°C
H ₂ O (% vol.)	combustion reactions & moisture	+0.2%
O ₂ (% vol.)	excess air / combustion stoichiometry	+0.4%
CO ₂ (% vol.)	carbon conversion & decarbonation contribution	-0.3%
NOx (mg/Nm ³ @ 10% O ₂ dry)	Thermal NOx/fuel NOx sensitivity	- 5%
CO (mg/Nm ³ @ 10% O ₂ dry)	combustion completeness indicator	-7%
Flue gas flow rate (Nm ³ /h)	global flow conservation	0,3%

✓ All 7 variables within acceptable engineering tolerance, model validated for oxy-combustion scenario simulation

CFD SIMULATION STRATEGY: FROM BASE CASE TO OXY-COMBUSTION

Aero-combustion is the established reference, the objective is to recover identical process outputs under oxy-combustion

CFD Simulation Outputs

Compared between base case (aero-combustion) and each oxy-combustion scenario:

- Radiative flux absorbed by clinker bed
- Temperature
- O₂ concentration
- CO₂, H₂O
- NO_x, CO

Optimisation Strategy

Reference Aero-combustion base case

Oxy-combustion scenarios - initial simulations

Burner parameter adjustments

Target - Process equivalence achieved

★ Key Indicator: Radiative Heat Flux

The radiative heat flux absorbed by the clinker bed governs energy transfer to the material, it is the direct driver of clinkering reactions and product quality.

Flame shape, temperature profile, KBE O₂%

SIMULATION MATRIX - 6 RUNS

Each run compared against the base case, focus on radiative heat flux on clinker bed

#	Run Name	O ₂ Injection Point	Description
1	Base Case	-	Aero-combustion reference, no O ₂ enrichment
2	Pure O ₂ - Burner Centre	Burner centreline	Pure O ₂ injected at burner centre.
3	High O ₂ SA - Low O ₂ PA	Secondary air (high)	High O ₂ enrichment in secondary air
4	High O ₂ PA - Low O ₂ SA	Primary air (high)	High O ₂ enrichment in primary air
5	Optimized Configuration	PA + SA (balanced)	Optimised O ₂ split
6	Sensitivity	Based on Run 5	O ₂ flow rate variation.

EFFECT OF CENTRAL O₂ INJECTION

CO profile(ppm). Vertical cross sections

Temperature profile (°C)- kiln axis plane

The endothermic Boudouard reaction - taken into account in the model with solid fuel - is confirmed:
 $C_s + CO_2 \rightarrow 2CO$
 produce more CO in oxy mode lowering temperature level and radiative heat flux

Temperature peak is lower with injection of O₂ at burner center. Higher kiln inlet temperature, means less exchange between flame and material bed

ESTIMATION OF FLAME LENGTH BASE ON ISO TEMPERATURE

At Iso-temperature (1800-2200°C) a significant flame length variations across runs, directly affecting the liquid phase position and clinkering conditions. Case 5 recovers the base case flame length, confirming process equivalence

RADIATIVE HEAT FLUX ANALYSIS

Radiative heat flux profiles confirm that case 5 (yellow curve) best matches the aero-combustion reference (red curve), both in peak magnitude and axial distribution along the kiln.

Other oxycombustion configurations show either flux deficit (base oxy, -7%) or excess (High PA O₂, +5%) shifting the liquid phase zone and risking clinker quality deviation.

KEY FINDINGS & CONCLUSIONS

What this study taught us, from CFD simulations to engineering deliverables

Boudouard Reaction Effect

$\text{CO}_2 + \text{Cs} \rightarrow 2\text{CO}$ reduces local O_2 availability and impacts flame temperature and exchange with clinker bed.

More $\text{O}_2 \neq$ Better Process

Balanced split recovers the base case more effectively.

Injection System Design

Dedicated injector design per point.

Patented Aero \rightarrow Oxy Transition Procedure

Step-by-step aero \rightarrow oxy transition procedure: stable kiln operation

✓ The optimised configuration recovers aero-combustion process equivalence, validating the oxy-combustion solution for industrial deployment on this 3 500 TPD cement kiln.

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